

EVALUATION OF IMPACTED DAMAGE OF FIBROUS COMPOSITE LAMINATES
BY ACOUSTIC EMISSION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

In this study damage in fibrous composite laminates subjected to longitudinal impact load was evaluated by an AE method. Test specimens contained three kinds of fibrous composite laminates: glass/epoxy, graphite/epoxy and aramid/epoxy laminates. Each laminate had four plies and their fiber orientations were three kinds of $[0_2]_S$, $[\pm 30]_S$ and $[\pm 45]_S$. In experiments impact loads corresponding to about 80% stress level of impact strength were applied to test specimens and then static tensile tests of these impacted specimens were performed along with measuring AE signals. For comparison, non-impacted specimens were also tested under the same conditions.

From the results of experiments, it has been known that the differences of the load bearing mechanism and effects of damage by impact load on failure processes reflected AE characteristics between the impacted and non-impacted fibrous composite laminates having different fiber orientations.

INTRODUCTION

It is important to know mechanical properties of fibrous composites under impact loading, because structures made up with fibrous composites are designed under more and more severe conditions lately. In addition the evaluation of damage of fibrous composites which suffered impact load is also important. Fibrous composites in structures are thought to be subjected to not only out-plane impact loads but also in-plane ones. There are lots of studies on damage of out-plane impacted fibrous composite laminates 1)2) but few studies on damage of in-plane impacted ones have been done. In the present study damage of fibrous composite laminates suffering the longitudinal impact load has been estimated by an AE method. Impact loads were applied to fibrous composite laminates, and then the AE signals were measured under the static tensile test. Consequently, damage of impacted fibrous composite laminates was estimated from the AE characteristics.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Specimen

The test specimens are shown in Fig.1. Three kinds of unidirectional prepreg sheets were used for them: glass/epoxy (Scotch Ply #1002), graphite/epoxy (Torayca P305-15) and aramid/epoxy (Kevlar PK05). And three kinds of stacking sequences were adopted: $[0_2]_S$, $[\pm 30]_S$ and $[\pm 45]_S$. Consequently, nine kinds of specimens were tested. The nomenclature is shown in Table 1.

2. Experimental procedures

The impact tests were performed with a drop-weight type testing machine designed in our laboratory. In the static tests, an Instron type testing machine was used, and the load was applied at a constant stress rate of 5 MPa/s. The static tensile tests were performed for specimens which subjected to 80% impact

Table 1 Nomenclature of specimen

Fig.1 Specimen geometry

Specimen	Prepreg	Stacking sequence
G0	glass/epoxy	[0 ₂] _s
G30	glass/epoxy	[±30] _s
G45	glass/epoxy	[±45] _s
C0	graphite/epoxy	[0 ₂] _s
C30	graphite/epoxy	[±30] _s
C45	graphite/epoxy	[±45] _s
A0	aramid/epoxy	[0 ₂] _s
A30	aramid/epoxy	[±30] _s
A45	aramid/epoxy	[±45] _s

load of the impact strength, with the AE measurement. Non-impacted specimens were also tested. An AE sensor used in the experiments was the resonance type one having a resonance frequency of 140 kHz. The AE signals from the AE sensor which were amplified with an amplifier went through a discriminator and then they were counted in a ring-down mode. They were stored in a desktop computer through an A/D convertor.

Table 2 Total AE counts and strength

Specimen	Static strength [MPa]		Total number of AE counts (x10 ⁴)		Impact strength [MPa]
	Non-impacted	Impacted	Non-impacted	Impacted	
G0	1023	1016	124.3	96.9	1470
G30	356	277	17.7	18.0	480
G45	199	173	46.8	45.9	304
C0	1548	1473	17.5	13.8	1989
C30	305	298	1.4	1.9	390
C45	148	121	16.9	10.2	160
A0	1143	1071	81.3	33.0	1497
A30	246	242	7.0	4.4	283
A45	82	77	18.2	7.8	104

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1.Total AE counts and tensile strength
 Static and impact strengths and total AE ring-down counts for all specimens are shown in Table 2. And Figs.2-4 show the relationship between the total AE ring-down counts and the tensile strength for the impacted and non-impacted specimens. In Fig.2, the results of [0₂]_s specimens are shown. The strength of the impacted specimen reduced for the C0 and A0 specimens, but did not reduce for the G0 in comparison with that of the non-impacted specimen. The total AE counts reduced for all [0₂]_s specimens. Especially the AE counts of the A0 specimen reduced considerably. The results of the [±30]_s specimens are shown in Fig.3. The strength of the impacted specimen

Fig.2 Relationship between total AE counts and tensile strength of [0₂]_s specimen

Fig.3 Relationship between total AE counts and tensile strength of [±30]_s specimen Fig.4 Relationship between total AE counts and tensile strength of [±45]_s specimen

reduced for the G30 specimen but did not change for the C30 and A30. The AE counts of the impacted specimen reduced for the A30 specimen, but slightly increased for the G30 and C30. In Fig.4, the results of the [±45]_s specimens are shown. The strength of the impacted specimen reduced for the G45 and C45 specimens, but did not change for the A45 in comparison with that of the non-impacted one. The AE counts reduced for the impacted C45 and A45 specimens, but almost never reduced for the G45. Briefly, the strength of the impacted specimen reduced and the AE counts reduced or almost never change.

2.Relation between AE count ratio and stress ratio

In Figs.5-13, the relation between the AE counts and the stress are shown for all kinds of specimens. In these figures, an abscissa is the stress ratio to the strength of the non-impacted specimen. An ordinate is the AE counts ratio to the total AE counts of the non-impacted specimen. The results for the [0₂]_s, [±30]_s and [±45]_s specimen are shown in Figs.5-7, 8-10 and 11-13, respectively. First, the results of [0₂]_s specimens are discussed. For the G0 specimen shown in Fig.5, the AE counts of the impacted specimen were a little fewer at each stress level than those of the non-impacted one. The relationship between the AE counts and the stress of the impacted and non-impacted specimen was almost the same. The results of the C0 specimen are shown in Fig.6. The impacted specimen had much fewer AE counts but had more increasing rate above about 0.75 stress level. As shown in Fig.7, the impacted A0 specimen had a little more AE counts below 0.4 stress level but above that much fewer AE counts than those of the non-impacted specimen. Next, the results of the [±30]_s specimens are examined. For the G30 specimen shown in Fig.8, the AE counts of the impacted specimen were a little fewer below about 0.6 stress level but above that had much more increasing rate till the failure occurred. The above matters also can be applied to the results of the C30 specimen except the stress level at which the AE counts of the impacted specimen became more than those of the non-impacted one.(Fig.9) For the A30 specimen shown in Fig.10, the AE counts of the impacted specimen were much fewer than those of the non-impacted specimen till the failure occurred. Finally, the results of the [±45]_s specimens are discussed. For the G45 specimen shown in Fig.11, the AE signals of the impacted specimen were measured at the lower stress in comparison with those of the non-impacted one. The manner of increase of the AE counts had no difference between the impacted and non-impacted specimens, while the stress level was

Fig.5 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (G0 specimen)

Fig.6 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (C0 specimen)

Fig.7 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (A0 specimen)

Fig.8 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (G30 specimen)

Fig.9 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (C30 specimen)

Fig.10 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (A30 specimen)

different. The same matters were also said for the C45 specimen.(Fig.12) For the A45 specimen shown in Fig.13, the AE signals of the impacted specimen initiated at the lower stress level and were much fewer than those of the non-impacted one.

Fig.11 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (G45 specimen)

Fig.12 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (C45 specimen)

Fig.13 Relationship between AE count ratio and stress ratio (A45 specimen)

Fig.14 Relationship between AE counts and stress (G30 and G45 specimens)

Fig.15 Relationship between AE counts and stress (C30 and C45 specimens)

Fig.16 Relationship between AE counts and stress (A30 and A45 specimens)

The relationships between the AE counts of $[\pm 30]_S$ and $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen for the same laminate are shown in Figs.14-16. In each figure, an abscissa is the tensile strength and an ordinate is the AE counts. For all kinds of the laminates, the AE signals of the $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen initiated at lower stress level and had much higher increasing rate than those of the $[\pm 30]_S$ specimen.

From the facts mentioned above, the followings have been known. The glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy laminates had the same change of AE characteristics in the impacted specimen. The AE counts of the impacted $[0_2]_S$ specimen reduced at the same stress level of the non-impacted specimen. On the other hand, the AE signals of the impacted $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen generated at the lower stress level than the non-impacted one. These changes of the AE counts can be explained as follows. In general, it is expected that damage which contained micro-cracking and fiber-matrix debonding took place when the specimen was impacted. In the $[0_2]_S$ specimen, fibers mainly beared the load, and so micro-cracking and fiber-matrix debonding in the impacted specimen did not develop so much as those in the non-impacted specimen. Since a lot of the AE signals are thought to generate due to micro-cracking and fiber-matrix debonding, the AE counts of the impacted $[0_2]_S$ specimen reduced. On the other hand, in the $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen, the load was transmitted through the interface between the fiber and the matrix, and then micro-cracking and fiber-matrix debonding in the impacted specimen developed at the lower stress level than those in the non-impacted specimen. This is reason why the AE signals of the impacted $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen generated at the lower stress than the non-impacted one. In the case of the $[\pm 30]_S$ specimen, an intermediately generating pattern of the AE signals between the $[0_2]_S$ and $[\pm 45]_S$ specimens was observed. The AE signals of the impacted specimen generated at the lower stress, and increased near the failure at higher increasing rate than those of the non-impacted one. This is thought to mean that at the low stress level, the generating pattern of the AE signals is similar to that of the $[0_2]_S$ specimen and near the failure it is similar to that of the $[\pm 45]_S$ specimen. The matters mentioned above were not applied to the aramid/epoxy laminate. In order to explain this reason, the further study on the relation between the interface and AE must be done.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to estimate the damage induced by longitudinal impact load in the fibrous composite materials, static tensile tests were performed with measurement of AE signals. Consequently, the followings were made clear.

- (1) The strength of the impacted fibrous composite laminates reduced, while the AE counts reduced or almost never changed by applying the impact load.
- (2) AE characteristics in each stacking sequence of the impacted glass/epoxy and graphite/epoxy laminates changed in a similar manner. But the aramid/epoxy laminates had different patterns.
- (3) It has been known that the difference of AE characteristics between the impacted and non-impacted fibrous composite laminates having different stacking sequences reflected the difference of the load bearing mechanisms and effects of damage by impact load on failure processes.

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